

Campaign name:

Shape sustainability

Slogans:

“Act today for a better tomorrow”

“Your idea your impact”

“Leave your mark”

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1. Summary

“Shape sustainability” is a youth-focused campaign aimed at empowering individuals 18-25 years of age to actively participate in building a sustainable future.

This campaign combines a street poster campaign with a strong social media presence to raise awareness spark creativity and encourage young people to share their own ideas for living sustainably.

Using visually appealing design language with bright nature-inspired colors, shape sustainability is designed to be both accessible and inspiring.

The campaign invites young people to have their say, participate in challenges, and help turn sustainable thinking into real action while also creating a direct link between youth voices and decision-makers.

By reaching audiences both in public spaces and online, the campaign leverages multiple touchpoints to maximize impact and visibility. Our goal is to create a platform where young people feel seen, heard, and empowered to shape the policies and practices that will define their future.

2. Goals and objectives

To engage and empower young people from low-income backgrounds in Utrecht (ages 18–25) by raising awareness about sustainable living and providing them with accessible platforms to share their ideas and influence decision-making

2.1. Specific objectives

- Reach at least **3,000–5,000 young people** through a creative street poster campaign in neighborhoods with high youth density and lower-income demographics (e.g., Overvecht, Kanaleneiland, Zuilen)
- Grow an online community of at least 1,000 followers on platforms like Instagram and TikTok, where campaign content, youth ideas, and sustainability tips are regularly shared in relatable formats (e.g., stories, reels, polls)

- Encourage Participation - Collect 200–300 ideas from young people on how to live sustainably, using low-barrier entry points such as scanning a QR code from posters, submitting ideas via Instagram, tiktok or WhatsApp, or dropping voice notes.
- Connect with Policymakers - Select and highlight the most promising ideas and present them to local policymakers and community leaders, ensuring the voices of underrepresented youth are part of sustainability conversations.
- Collaborate with Local Networks - Align the campaign with the company’s current partnerships in Utrecht by integrating “Shape Sustainability” into ongoing youth and community initiatives. The campaign will amplify these efforts by increasing visibility and youth engagement, creating shared value and deeper impact across platforms.

3. Target audience

Age group: Primary focus young people aged 18-25 years

This group includes students, job seekers, and young adults navigating independence—many of whom are already aware of sustainability but lack platforms to act or be heard.

Location: Urban parts of Utrecht, especially areas with high youth density and socioeconomic diversity. Some targeted neighborhoods include: Overvecht, Kanaleneiland, Lombok, Zuilen as these areas are known for their younger populations, multicultural communities and lower average income levels.

Demographics: Youth from low-income households with diverse ethnic and cultural backgrounds, who often have fewer opportunities to engage in formal sustainability programs but are a vital part of urban fabric and could bring fresh perspectives to sustainability.

They represent a mix of students (university, MBO, HBO), part time workers, and young people transitioning to work force.

4. Campaign messaging

“Your idea your impact” It is short, punchy and powerful, it gives the sensation of speaking directly to the person reading it making them feel seen and important. Connecting idea and impact makes the campaign feel purposeful and not just symbolic.

“Sustainability is not a luxury is a necessity”- It’s short, powerful and shifts perspective. Many people associate sustainability with expensive products like organic food, electric cars etc, making it feel out of reach so this message flips it saying that sustainability isn’t optional, but something everyone depends on. It is memorable and sparks action.

5. Engagement Strategy

This campaign uses two main engagement strategies: street posters that serve as tools to raise awareness on sustainability, and invite for action and involvement in shaping sustainability. And the second one social media or digital platforms through which young people can learn more about sustainability and share their perspectives or ideas on how they want to live sustainably.

Two kind of posters will be used: **Awareness posters** and **Action posters**.

The goal of the first type of poster will be to catch attention, introduce the message, while the second poster’s goal is to give specific instructions or invite participation in “shaping sustainability”.

Awareness poster’ slogans examples: *“Tomorrow is sustainable”*, *“Sustainability is not a luxury is a necessity”*

Action poster’s slogans examples: *“Your idea your impact”*, *“Leave your mark”*, *“Act today for a better tomorrow”*.

Awareness posters will be placed in high-visibility spots to grab attention: High-traffic public areas like bus stops, train stations, street poles near markets etc.

Action posters will be placed nearby where people pause and have time to read, e.g near and inside schools, youth centers, libraries, cafeterias etc.

A mix of print sizes will be used, A1 or A2 for outdoors and A3 or A4 for indoors.

Platforms like Instagram or tiktok will be used to deliver different content types like: Challenges, polls, short videos, memes, stories.

Through posters which will contain QR codes and hashtags, young people will be encouraged to share their ideas or projects on sustainability.

6. Visual identity

The tree will serve as this campaign's visual identity.

Trees symbolize growth and development, just like trees that start small and grow over time, actions and ideas on sustainability can do the same. Its branches symbolize many paths or aspects of sustainability.

Their ability to regenerate symbolizes cycles of life, restoration and hope.

Trees literally fight climate change by absorbing CO2.

The tree shape will be used across posters, social media icons etc, and will be the identifying symbol of the campaign.

The campaign includes the logos of ethicschool and duurzaamutrecht to reflect the collaborative nature of this project. QR codes will lead to websites of the consultancy company ethicschool and the informal network of Sustainable Utrecht 2030 Duurzaam Utrecht as the focal point of engaging youth and policymakers in dialogue and collaboration on sustainability. They are placed at the bottom right of each poster, positioned alongside their respective logos.

The posters will contain hashtags

(#ethicschool#duurzaamutrecht2030#shapesustainability#yourideayourimpact) that young people will use when sharing their ideas or perspectives on Instagram or tiktok.

To strengthen the campaign's presence across platforms, the landing pages accessed through the QR codes should be designed to feature the campaign slogans. These slogans should switch dynamically or rotate to maintain visual engagement and reinforce the campaign message.

To ensure campaigns reach and emotional connection with young people, the campaign could involve well-known and loved local figures (artists, creators, activists, athletes) who resonate with the 18-25 age group.

These individuals would be invited to post short, authentic videos on platforms like Instagram or tiktok sharing how they live sustainably, highlighting sustainability-related challenges in their daily lives, or calling others to take small but meaningful actions and share ideas.

Their posts would feature the campaign slogan and visuals, and include campaign hashtags to increase visibility and encourage sharing among their networks.

7. Poster concepts

8. Amplification for policymakers

Through a summary booklet of collected ideas the vision of young people will be documented and then handed to local officials.

To raise visibility of this collection of ideas, they can be displayed as reels tagged to local officials or partner with a local council to host a hearing event.

9. Impact measurement

The impact of the campaign can be measured by some indicators:

- The number of entries submitted
- The demographic of participants like age group, location, background etc
- Social media reach, in terms of number of users who saw the content
- Follower and views growth across platforms during the campaign period